

NON-REMOVABLE DENTURES

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Abstract: Among temporary structures used after the dental implant and bone grafting, tooth cap is the most effective option because during the preparation of the temporary structures, we mainly focus on functionality of the prosthesis, the possibility of a longlasting as well as comfortable use and on its aesthetics, which meets the requirements of both the doctor and the patient.

Key words: non-removable, dentures, prosthetics, implant.

After the implants are installed, the patient can be prosthetics with removable and non-removable orthopedic structures. Most patients, when motivated for dental implantation, explain their consent to surgical measures and the multi-stage nature of dental manipulations and financial costs by unwillingness to be prosthetically removable structures. Prosthetics on implants with traditional bridges. provides effective restoration of the integrity of the dentition. In this case, the fastening is carried out on special dental cements or their analogues. In cases where the location of dental implants cannot provide cosmetic prosthetics, or it is necessary to perform artificial teeth of a smaller size without reducing the height of the bite, artificial bridges are used.

However, in practical healthcare when used of these structures arise problems, especially if there are complications with a dental implant. Treatment of these complications is effective in the absence of dental teeth in this area prosthesis, as access to pathological area, as well as eliminates the load on the implant adjacent teeth. These problems, helps decide the use of conditionally removable dentures.

It should be noted that some of the proposed conditionally fixed structures can be considered as an improvement of removable structures, which should be evaluated as physiological (needs, To the tiller).

Conditionally non-removable dentures of the lamellar type consist of a base, an artificial gum and standard plastic teeth. The basis of such structures, like artificial gums, is made of basic plastics. But in order to ensure the strength of the prosthesis structure and indifference to the effect on the tissues of the prosthetic bed, the option of using a metal base is being considered. The connection element of the dental implant and the conditionally fixed prosthesis is successfully carried out on an artificial tooth, crown or base. This is mainly determined by the location of the dental

an implant in the jaw. This design provides for the restoration of the dentition throughout.

The use of a conditionally non-removable artificial crown type prosthesis makes it easy to prepare the oral cavity for any dental prosthetics options that may arise as a result of subsequent tooth extractions on the jaw. After removing such a prosthesis, it is possible to perform a new prosthetics with a modified dental structure on the remaining dental implant, depending on the dental situation that has arisen.

The conditionally non-removable structure is attached to the dental implant by a special system of devices having various solutions to this problem. A mechanical connection should be considered as an option that allows you to solve the main task of this prosthetics: screw, bolt and wrench. The use of a special standard screw allows you to connect the implants and the abutment into a single system. It can also be successfully used for fastening and conditionally fixed prostheses. Only the screw should be taken into account the thickness of the fixed structure. The hole above the screw it is closed with a special filling material, and the patient cannot remove this structure on his own. But if necessary, a doctor can always do it. This fixation – screw and bolt – is solved by using standard blanks.

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